

Participant	Role	Organization	Org. Size	Org. Domain	Software Type	Gender	Years Experience
P1	Developer	O1	Medium	Productivity	SaaS, B2C	Male	4
P2	Developer					Female	4
P3	Developer	O2	Small	Web Design	B2B	Male	2
P4	Product Manager	O3	Medium	Communication	B2B	Female	5
P5	Product Manager	O4	Medium	Finance	B2B	Female	8
P6	Developer	O5	Medium	Reservation Management	SaaS, B2B	Male	2
P7	Customer Success					Female	8
P8	Developer					Male	8
P9	Product Manager	O6	Large	Health	Enterprise	Female	12
P10	Product Manager	O7	Large	Finance	SaaS, B2B	Female	10
P11	Product Manager					Female	9
P12	Developer					Female	4
P13	Developer	O7	Large	Finance	SaaS, B2B	Male	8
P14	Developer	O8	Medium	Hospitality	SaaS, B2B	Male	9
P15	Customer Success					Female	13
P16	Developer	O9	Small	Gaming	B2C	Male	7
P17	Developer					Male	5
P18	Developer	O10	Small	Communication	B2B	Female	1
P19	Product Manager	O11	Medium	Finance	SaaS	Male	15
P20	Quality Assurance					Male	4
P21	Developer	O12	Medium	Reservation Management	SaaS, B2B	Female	5
P22	Customer Success					Female	13
P23	Developer	O13	Medium	Tourism	SaaS, B2B	Male	11
P24	Quality Assurance					Male	4
P25	Product Manager	O14	Large	Search / Advertising	Enterprise	Male	14
P26	Product Manager	O15	Medium	Communication	B2B	Female	17
P27	Developer					Male	10
P28	Product Manager	O16	Medium	Finance	SaaS, B2B	Male	12
P29	Developer					Male	12
P30	Developer	O17	Small	Real Estate	SaaS, B2B	Female	10
P31	Product Manager	O18	Medium	Gaming	B2C	Male	8
P32	Product Manager	O19	Large	Cloud Services	Enterprise	Male	11
P33	Quality Assurance	O20	Medium	Gaming	B2C	Male	3

Table 1: Participants' Roles, Gender, Years Experience, Organization, and Organizational Information including size, domain, and type of software.

Figure 1: The number of new codes generated at each of 33 interviews.

*authors coded separately after establishing shared understanding (see Methodology)